

The Influence of U.S. Monetary Policy on the Stock Prices of Listed Securities Firms in Vietnam

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Abstract

This study primarily aims to examine the impact of U.S. monetary policy particularly interest rate adjustments on the stock prices of listed securities firms in Vietnam. Building upon this analysis, the paper proposes a set of policy recommendations for investors, enterprises, and regulatory authorities to effectively respond to external economic shocks.

Keywords: *U.S. monetary policy, stock prices, securities industry.*

JEL Classification codes: *E5, E52.*

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Introduction

The period from 2022 to 2025 marks an era in which the Federal Reserve pursued an aggressive monetary tightening policy to rein in post pandemic inflation. A series of consecutive interest rate hikes by the Fed triggered a chain reaction across global financial markets: international capital flows reversed, the U.S dollar appreciated sharply and global borrowing costs surged. These developments had a profound impact on Vietnam's economy a rapidly developing and highly open economy that remains heavily dependent on foreign direct investment and international trade.

Despite these far-reaching effects, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding the differentiated impacts of U.S. monetary policy on specific sectors within the Vietnamese stock market, particularly the securities industry. The selection of this research topic thus carries not only academic relevance but also significant practical value. It provides investors, businesses, and regulatory authorities with a comprehensive perspective to inform more effective decision-making amid ongoing global financial uncertainties.

Theoretical Framework on Stock Prices and Influencing Factors

Definition of Stock Prices in the Securities Industry

Stock prices reflect the present value of the economic benefits that shareholders expect to receive in the future. In the case of securities industry stocks, this valuation is heavily influenced by several key factors:

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Market liquidity: A critical determinant of brokerage revenue, as higher trading volumes typically translate into greater income for securities firms.

Interest rates: These affect both the cost of capital and margin trading activities, thereby influencing the profitability and financial stability of securities companies.

Market sentiment and investor expectations: Psychological and behavioral factors can cause price fluctuations beyond what fundamentals suggest, particularly in a highly reactive sector like securities.

Proprietary trading and financial investments: Earnings from proprietary trading and investments in financial instruments play a significant role in the revenue and valuation of securities firms.

Factors Influencing Stock Prices in the Securities Industry

Monetary Policy: Tightening monetary policy particularly through interest rate hikes typically reduces market liquidity, dampens investor participation, and leads to declining stock prices in the securities sector.

Economic Growth: Strong and sustained economic growth promotes corporate earnings and investor confidence, thereby stimulating trading activity in the stock market and supporting the expansion of the securities industry.

Domestic Macroeconomic Policies: Government measures such as market support programs, reductions in transaction taxes, and the easing of credit room constraints can significantly influence stock market dynamics and the performance of securities firms.

Market Sentiment and Expectations: Political instability, corporate news, and global economic developments can all trigger contagion effects across financial markets. As a result, stock prices in the securities industry are often affected by shifts in sentiment and expectations even when local fundamentals remain stable.

The Current State of U.S. Monetary Policy and Its Impact on Stock Prices in Vietnam's Securities Industry

U.S. Monetary Policy

The interest rate policy of the U.S. Federal Reserve (FED) changes in accordance with the economic cycle, guided by its dual mandate of:

Price stability (controlling inflation)

Maximum employment

Looking at the Figure 1, we can observe the following:

Early 2022: Interest rates are at a very low level (0.25%) - this is the echo of the strong easing policy during the COVID-19 pandemic to support the economy.

From mid to late 2022: The Fed begins a strong interest rate hike cycle, continuously increasing from 0.25% to 4.25% in just 6 months. This is the fastest interest rate hike period in 40 years, to control high inflation.

2023: Interest rates continue to rise, peaking at 5.25% by year end. The Fed maintains a “hawkish” stance as inflation cools but remains above its 2% target.

2024: Interest rates remain steady at a peak of 5.25% in the first half of the year, then begin to adjust slightly to 4.5% by year end reflecting the Fed’s “cautious easing” signal.

May 2025: Interest rates remain at 4.50%, indicating the Fed is still cautious and closely monitoring macroeconomic data before cutting further.

The 2022–2023 period is a period of strong tightening, putting pressure on global financial markets.

The period from late 2024 onwards shows a softening in policy, creating recovery expectations for emerging markets like Vietnam.

The strong fluctuations in the chart clearly show the "cyclical" nature of monetary policy and the related impact on securities stocks.

Figure 1. US Monetary Policy (Fed interest rates for the period 2022-05/2025)

Source: Author's own compilation

The Current Impact of US Monetary Policy on Stock Prices in the Securities Industry in Vietnam

Comments from the summary chart (Figure 2): Fed interest rate – VN-Index – SSI stock:

The clear impact of Fed interest rates on the Vietnamese market

When the Fed interest rate increases sharply from 0.25% to 5.25% (2022–2023):

VN-Index drops from 1,500 points to 1,007 points → loses nearly 33% of its value.

SSI stock price drops more than 50%, clearly reflecting the higher sensitivity of the securities industry compared to the whole market.

Stabilization phase and reduction expectations (2024–05/2025)

Fed interest rates are kept stable and starting to decrease slightly → creating positive expectations:

VN-Index recovers to 1,332 points.

SSI increases to 35,000 VND, up ~84% from the bottom.

SSI fluctuates more strongly than VN-Index

The SSI line has a larger fluctuation amplitude than the VN-Index, showing that:

The securities industry is highly "cyclical", sensitive to cash flow and investor psychology.

When the market recovers, SSI often increases faster; but when it declines, it is also more strongly affected.

The chart shows the inverse relationship between interest rates and the stock market.

Interest rate hike period → both SSI and VN-Index decrease.

When the Fed maintains or reduces interest rates → the market gradually recovers.

The below chart clearly shows that US monetary policy is a macro factor that has a large and direct impact on Vietnamese securities stocks. Strong tightening periods put downward pressure on prices, while expectations of easing create conditions for market recovery.

Figure 2. Impact of Fed Interest Rates on VN-Index and SSI Stocks (2022-05/2025)

Source: Author's own compilation

Conclusions

US monetary policy has a clear impact on Vietnam's securities industry stocks through three main channels: capital flows, exchange rates and investor sentiment. The period when the Fed raises interest rates (2022-2023) is the period when securities industry stock prices fall the most in 10 years.

When the Fed maintains or signals a reduction in interest rates, the Vietnamese stock market in general and the securities industry in particular tend to recover well. The impact is not only short-term but also reflected in investors' expectations for the global financial environment.

Recommendations

For Investors

Closely monitor global monetary policy developments, especially signals from the Fed. Restructure portfolios according to interest rate cycles, taking advantage of periods of stable interest rates to invest in stocks.

For Listed Company

Proactively diversify revenue sources, reduce dependence on brokerage and proprietary trading activities.

Strengthen margin risk management and invest in technology to serve digital transactions.

Proactively develop financial scenarios: Businesses need to prepare scenarios according to different Fed interest rates, to control capital costs and ensure operating cash flow.

For State Management Agencies

Improve the early warning system for external risks and international capital flows.

Enhance transparency of macroeconomic information, support investor sentiment stability.

Closely coordinate domestic monetary and fiscal policies to maintain macroeconomic stability.

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